

X-ROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D7.7

Final holistic assessment of potential X-ROTOR economic impact

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

Deliverable 7.7: “Final holistic assessment of potential X-Rotor economic impact” aims to provide a regional economic impact analysis of the X-ROTOR technology in comparison with traditional horizontal axis offshore wind turbines (HAWTs). An assessment of the relationship between offshore wind levelized costs reductions undertaken in Devoy McAuliffe *et al.* (2023): “Modelled LCOE for the X-ROTOR” from WP6, is used to provide input to a system-wide economic modelling framework. The results show a comparative analysis of the aggregate economic metrics including GDP and Jobs.

The I-JEDI model used is an Input Output framework used to measure regional economic impacts of renewable energy technologies. Three economic regions are studied Ireland, UK, and Spain. Considering information from D6.2 we assume two market scenarios, one with deployment of 5GW of offshore wind in the three regions to compare X-Rotor and HWATs, and a second scenario with 100% deployment of X-Rotor in all offshore wind generation in the UK so that direct comparisons may be made with the computable general equilibrium (CGE) model in Deliverable 7.8 (Williamson and Allan, 2024).

List of acronyms

CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CGE	Computable General Equilibrium
CSO	Central Statistics Office (IE)
D	Deliverable
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GVA	Gross Value Added
GW	Gigawatt
HAWT	Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine
I-JEDI	International Jobs and Economic Development Impact model
INE	Instituto Nacional de Estadística (ES)
IO	Input Output
LCOE	Levelised Cost of Electricity
MWh	Megawatt Hour
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
ONS	Office for National Statistics (UK)
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
UK	United Kingdom
WP	Work Package
XRC	X-ROTOR Concept

1 Introduction

This report originates from WP7-Environmental and Social-Economic impact of the X-ROTOR project. The aim is to assess the regional economic impacts from the X-ROTOR concept in comparison with traditional horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs). The approach taken is a bottom-up analysis which involves analysing individual variables at the lowest possible level of detail and aggregating the estimates to arrive at the economic impacts' summary totals. The assessment takes a case study in Europe, analysing the deployment of X-ROTOR and HAWTs in three countries, Ireland, United Kingdom, and Spain.

Most regional economic impact assessments of projects use employment ratios, computable general equilibrium (CGE), or Input-Output (IO) models, as explained by (Jenniches *et al.*, 2019; Landry *et al.*, 2013; Stefek *et al.*, 2019). The CGE models are used to assess top-down effects such as the effect of energy policy (Fattahi *et al.*, 2023). To complement the CGE approach taken by our colleagues in the University of Strathclyde, this report follows a bottom-up approach and uses an IO model.

To capture overall economic impacts, IO models have been widely used since their establishment by Leontief, (1936). The IO model uses direct economic effects from industrial economic activities and indirect effects on the industries' suppliers, it then returns the interactions of different industries in an economic system. However, the challenge is the huge amount of data required to create an up-to-date regional specific IO model. We use a simplified Input-Output methodology as a bottom-up approach to assess the regional economic impact of deploying 5GW of wind farm capacity. The International Jobs and Economic Development Impact (I-JEDI) model is used in this study.

The methodology used is similar to Darghouth *et al.*, (2020) which analyses the economic impact of distributed photovoltaic cells in Indonesia, and Woollacott *et al.*, (2023) for renewable energy investment in Kenya. The scenario and data follow results from Deliverable 6.2 (Devoy McAuliffe *et al.*, 2023). This work, which originates from WP6 of the X-ROTOR project, provides input on the reductions in levelized costs of electricity from the X-ROTOR concept which informs this economic analysis.

The document is organised as follows: Section 2 gives an overview of the model used for the analysis explaining key modelling assumptions. Section 3 details the data used including an overview of the region-specific IO tables. Section 4 presents result of the analysis and Section 5 concludes.

2 The I-JEDI Model

The I-JEDI model was first developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) with support from the U.S. Agency for International Development, as a free tool for assessing the economic impacts of renewables around the world. The model estimates the gross domestic product, employment, earnings, and output from the construction and operation of renewable energy projects across the domestic supply chain and channels the results to other sectors like manufacturing and banking services. The I-JEDI model has three custom regions with different IO matrices that can be edited to match different economic regions in the world. We adjust the model to fit the three countries used in this report by using the current (2021) IO tables.

The region chosen for analysis is customised by 37 sectors which capture direct, indirect, and induced effect from the project investment (Table 1). Direct impacts represent the economic impacts that are directly linked to construction, operation, and decommissioning of the project for example employment on the construction site. Indirect effects are connected to the business in the value chain, and induced effects occur when workers involved in construction and operations of the wind project spend their money in other economic activities.

	Economic sector
1	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing
2	Mining and quarrying
3	Manufacturing: Food products, beverages, and tobacco
4	Manufacturing: Textiles, textile products, leather, and footwear
5	Manufacturing: Wood and products of wood and cork
6	Manufacturing: Pulp, paper, paper products, printing, and publishing
7	Manufacturing: Coke, refined petroleum products and nuclear fuel
8	Manufacturing: Chemicals and chemical products
9	Manufacturing: Rubber and plastics products
10	Manufacturing: Other non-metallic mineral products
11	Manufacturing: Basic metals
12	Manufacturing: Fabricated metal products except machinery and equipment
13	Manufacturing: Machinery and equipment not classified elsewhere
14	Manufacturing: Office, accounting, and computing machinery
15	Manufacturing: Electrical machinery and apparatus not classified elsewhere
16	Manufacturing: Radio, television, and communication equipment
17	Manufacturing: Medical, precision, and optical instruments
18	Manufacturing: Motor vehicles, trailers, and semi-trailers
19	Manufacturing: Other transport equipment

	Economic sector
20	Manufacturing: Manufacturing not classified elsewhere; recycling
21	Electricity, gas, and water supply
22	Construction
23	Wholesale and retail trade; repairs
24	Hotels and restaurants
25	Transport and storage
26	Post and telecommunications
27	Finance and insurance
28	Real estate activities
29	Renting of machinery and equipment
30	Computer and related activities
31	Research and development
32	Other Business Activities
33	Public admin. and defence; compulsory social security
34	Education
35	Health and social work
36	Other community, social and personal services
37	Private households with employed persons

Table 1: List of products by industry in the model

In a technical form, the IO analysis is expressed as

$$x = Ax + y \quad (1)$$

where x represents the vector of total gross output of a sector and y represents the vector of final demand and includes domestic consumer spending, assets, changes in inventories, and exports. “ A ” represents the matrix of intermediate consumption per unit of output, and I is the identity matrix.

The Leontief inverse $L = (I - A)^{-1}$ is determined from the following mathematical transformation (Equations 2 and 3):

$$x = Ax + y \quad (1)$$

$$y = x - Ax \quad (2)$$

$$y = (I - A) x \quad (3)$$

with I as the identity matrix, then $x = (I - A)^{-1}y$, with x , the output triggered by a given demand y , the corresponding gross value added can be derived using country and sector-specific ratios of GVA to output.

Apart from the IO tables and Leontief inverse matrix, the model requires specific inputs from the project. These include: the currency year, later to be interpreted by adjusting for inflation and the currency used; the total capacity of the project to be deployed with the corresponding number of turbines and the cost of equipment, construction, and OPEX. Each variable must be matched with the specific economic region where operation is taking place.

Variable	Ireland (%)	Spain (%)	UK (%)
% Manufactured and Purchased in the region			
Turbine (Generator, Gearbox, Nacelle) HAWT	30	70	90
Turbine (Generator, Gearbox, Nacelle) X-ROTOR	40	80	100
Blades HAWT	20	60	80
Blades X-ROTOR	60	70	100
Tower HAWT	70	80	90
Tower X-ROTOR	70	80	90
Equipment Shipping/Transportation (both)	100	100	100
% Purchased in the region			
Electrical Balance of Plant (both)	80	90	90
Construction (Excluding Site Improvements) (both)	100	100	100
% Spent in the region			
Engineering and Other Professional Services (both)	60	90	90
Site Improvement (<i>i.e.</i> , Road Construction) (both)	100	100	100
% Spent in the region			
Plant Operations (staff, equipment such as trucks) (both)	80	90	90
Replacement Parts (both)	40	80	100

Table 2: Project's input assumptions.

Assumptions are made by considering the percentage share of each cost to the specific country. In the sectors 13 and 22, equipment and construction, we refer to how much of the turbine components are manufactured and purchased in each region in Table 2. While Ireland has a significant amount of industrial activity, little of it is in heavy industry, vehicle manufacturing or shipbuilding which are the types of industry which would be expected to take up work on offshore wind. The UK already has active blade manufacturing in Hull¹ and has approximately 15 GW² of offshore wind installed. Spain³ is the second largest car manufacturer in Europe and is at an advanced stage of planning for its offshore wind deployment⁴. On operation and maintenance, the UK and Spain lead Ireland with more money going to their economy since they have more local staff and

¹ See [Powering ahead in the UK: Siemens Gamesa to double offshore blade facility](#) and [Siemens – Green Port Hull: A £310m renewable energy project | Mace \(macegroup.com\)](#) accessed 21-Feb-2024

² See [Wind Energy Statistics - RenewableUK](#), accessed 21-Feb-2024

³ See [Car Makers Pour Money Into Spain](#), accessed 21-Feb-2024

⁴ See [Spain maps out first boundaries for offshore wind parks | Reuters](#), accessed 21-Feb-2024

replacement parts than Ireland. The pattern is therefore that more local spending will happen in UK than in Spain and more in Spain than in Ireland. In addition, since the X-ROTOR turbines are smaller, more local production of X-ROTOR is expected than HAWTs. For a description of how the percentages were allocated, see Table 2 above.

The research and development stage is the first phase in the life cycle of a wind turbine project. However, it is difficult to analyse all the enterprises involved in this stage, from research bodies, planning and permission bodies, community consents, environmental protection authorities, land leasing, bidding auctions, and other enterprises involved in the renewable energy industry. The analysis presented here is limited to the four stages, manufacturing, installation, O&M, and decommissioning (Table 3). The data needed for the analysis are IO tables for each economic region, the assumptions for local spending in Table 2 and the input parameters listed in Table 4. We add the cost of decommissioning to CAPEX to match the I-JEDI model requirement.

Time	R&D	Manufacturing	Installation	O&M	Decommissioning
A	Planning activities				
B		Turbines			
C			capacity added consecutively each year	Transport cost, repair cost, staff cost, lost revenue	
D					Average €/MW OR Staff, crane hire, selling

Table 3: Wind Project Lifecycle

2.1 IO Tables and Leontief inverse matrices

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) data was used for region specific IO tables. This source of data was chosen as the data format match the I-JEDI model economic sectors. The OECD data are sourced from OECD, 2024. This data is used to fill the direct and indirect requirement part of the model.

The model also requires information on annual average earning, gross domestic product, and total labour compensation per sector. Statistical bodies of each country provided this information. In Ireland, this was the Central Statistics Office (CSO), in Spain, the Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE) and in the United Kingdom, the Office for National Statistics (ONS).

2.2 Wind Project Inputs

Deliverable 6.2, (Devoy McCuliffe et al, 2023) of the X-ROTOR project provides the basic inputs that differentiate traditional HAWTs and X-ROTOR. Generally, X-ROTOR is shown to have lower costs and in particular lower levelised cost of energy than typical HAWTs. Lower capital cost for an X-ROTOR turbine is a result of having no gearbox, no requirement for a bespoke multi-pole generator, and no twist in blade designs (Leithead *et al.*, 2019). The X-ROTOR turbines OPEX costs are expected to be less than the HAWTs due to the power take-off systems being situated closer to sea level, meaning that almost all repair and maintenance operations can be completed without the need for a heavy-lift vessel, which accounts for half the vessel charter costs for HAWT wind farms (McMorland *et al.*, 2022).

In this analysis we use an average of the LCOEs modelled for offshore HAWTs from Deliverable 6.2, (Devoy McAuliffe *et al.*, 2023), giving a figure of 50.415€/MWh and an estimated LCOE for X-ROTOR of 46.74€/MWh. (See Figure 6.1 on page 26 of 28 of Deliverable 6.2.) Table 4 provides a list of each input used for the two technologies, X-ROTOR, and the traditional offshore wind turbine. A 5 GW capacity is studied as it represents the renewable energy “Future Framework” target for offshore wind energy in Ireland as presented by the Department of the Environmental, Climate and Communication (DECC, 2024). As Ireland represents the smallest region of the three economies, then this capacity, 5 GW is used as a benchmark for all three countries, allowing comparisons to be made between X-Rotor and HAWTs on an equal basis.

Variable	X-ROTOR	HAWTs
All LCOE figures are from Devoy McAuliffe <i>et al.</i> (2023)		
Project capacity = 5GW		
LCOE €/MWh	46.74	50.42
€ m		
Turbine (Generator, Gearbox, Nacelle)	2,671	2,881
Blades	666	719
Tower	1,273	1,373
Equipment Shipping/Transportation	230	249
Electrical Balance of Plant	2,597	2,801
Construction (Excluding Site Improvements)	844	910
Engineering and Other Professional Services	1,651	1,781
Site Improvement (<i>i.e.</i>, Road Construction)	0	0
Plant Operations (staff, equipment such as trucks)	1,524	1,644
Replacement Parts	4,968	5,359
Civil Works (Access Road Maintenance, Etc.)	0	0

Table 4: Wind project inputs in € millions

3 Results

This section presents the results of the analysis. Four areas are considered to capture the economic impact of deploying each technology to specific country: jobs created, earnings, total output, and GDP (value added). The number of jobs created are weighted to each country's working population in this analysis (People aged from 16 to 65). All other categories are normalised as a percentage of gross domestic product.

Results from this analysis are similar to most IO analysis findings using direct effect, indirect effect, and induced effect. For example, as quoted from the NREL user guide⁵ *“generator manufacturer that purchases copper wire, the direct effect would be the purchase of a generator and the indirect effect would be the purchase of copper wire by the generator manufacturer. Indirect effects could include business-to-business services, natural resources, and any other activity that is supported by industry expenditures. Other indirect economic impacts from the example above include purchasing a coil-winding machine and hiring a consultant to diagnose faulty generators. The induced impact is activity that could occur from household expenditures made by worker earnings that are supported by direct and indirect impacts. For example, if workers from the generator manufacturer and the wire manufacturer go to a restaurant, their payments to the restaurant would be the induced impact”*.

3.1 Jobs

Table 5 presents the number of total number of jobs required for each technology in the three economic regions. On average over the three countries there are 10% fewer jobs required to generate 5GW using X-Rotor technology compared with HAWTs. This is because X-ROTOR technology delivers energy more cheaply than traditional HAWTs. In Ireland there is a small 1.8 % higher number of jobs for the X-Rotor technology than for HAWTs, this small difference is due to more indirect jobs from X-ROTOR technology than for HAWTs.

The total number of jobs created in the UK and Spain is on average 4,709 for both, this is 60% higher than the number of jobs on average for Ireland for both technologies. This is due to the expectation that the UK and Spain have the engineering and manufacturing jobs already in place which can take on X-ROTOR or HAWT deployment. The small jobs figures in Ireland can also be explained by the smaller percentage of money allocated to the Irish economy, see Table 2. However, the percentage of jobs created within the total work force in Ireland is considerably bigger than the other regions because of the smaller working population present in the country. In all regions, indirect effects account for more than 80% of the jobs created whilst there are no jobs created in induced effect. The large percentage of direct effect in Spain and the UK is due

⁵ See [User Guide for the International Jobs and Economic Development Impacts Model \(nrel.gov\)](#) accessed 27-Feb-2024

to the greater presence of industries relevant to the deployment of offshore wind (e.g., engineering). Note the size of the work force in each country in 2022 in millions: Ireland 2.67, UK 34.38, and Spain 23.69 (World Bank⁶). The gross annual salary in Ireland was €46,264 in 2022 (CSO.ie); in Spain the gross annual salary was €25,897 in 2021 (PR AWSS 2021 (ine.es), which allowing for Spanish inflation⁷ in 2021 of 6.6%, gives €27,606; UK Gross annual salary was €37,276 ONS.gov.uk⁸ using the mean annual conversion rate of GB 0.85276⁹ from the Irish Central Bank.

The lower numbers of jobs required for X- ROTOR is not a surprise as it requires less investment because the LCOE of X-Rotor is 3.68€/MW less than for HAWTs. For a 5GW project capacity this is equivalent to a reduction in costs of €120 million over the life of the project.

Country	Effect	X-ROTOR	Jobs to work force (%)	HAWTs	Jobs to work force (%)
Ireland	Direct	395	0.0148	405	0.0152
	Indirect	2570	0.0963	2,507	0.0939
	Induced	-	-	-	0
	Total	2965	0.1111	2,912	0.1091
UK	Direct	624	0.0018	660	0.0019
	Indirect	3702	0.0108	4,593	0.0134
	Induced	-	0	-	0
	Total	4,326	0.0126	5,252	0.0153
Spain	Direct	691	0.0029	731	0.0031
	Indirect	3,699	0.0156	4,137	0.0175
	Induced	-	0	-	0
	Total	4390	0.0185	4,868	0.0205

Table 5: Number of Jobs created from Construction and O&M averaged per year of project lifetime.

3.2 Earnings

This section presents the money obtained in return for labour (Table 6). The values are normalised as a percentage of GDP to aid interpretation and for easy comparison of different economic regions. There is a difference of 0.0003% for Ireland with X-Rotor having a slightly larger effect. For UK the difference is 0.0008% and 0.0009% for Spain with HAWTs showing larger impacts. This reflects the slightly larger number of jobs required in Ireland and the reduced numbers in Spain and the UK.

⁶ See <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.TLF.TOTL.IN> accessed 27-Feb-2024

⁷ See <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/2995521/14176359/2-20012022-AP-EN.pdf/ce642dc8-1f96-fb6e-a7fc-a667762c5d37> accessed 26-Feb-2024

⁸ See <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/employmentandemployeetypes/bulletins/averageweeklyearningsingreatbritain/december2022> accessed 26-Feb-2024

⁹ See <https://www.centralbank.ie/statistics/interest-rates-exchange-rates/exchange-rates> accessed 26-Feb-2024

Ireland shows the highest total earnings as a percentage of GDP, indicating a significant contribution from the projects, particularly in indirect earnings. This is due to Ireland's smaller GDP. Similarly, the earnings per GDP for Spain is larger than the UK.

The difference in countries total GDP plays a great role for these results. The gross domestic product (GDP) of Ireland is relatively small, compared to the larger economies of Spain and the UK. Note that the GDP figures are €3,654 billion, €2,209 billion, and €651 billion for UK, Spain, and Ireland respectively (2022, OECD¹⁰). Another factor to consider is the number of jobs created in each region, recall Table 5.

Country	Effect	X-ROTOR		HAWTs	
		€ millions	% GDP	€ millions	% GDP
Ireland	Direct	15	0.0023	15	0.0023
	Indirect	90	0.0139	88	0.0136
	Induced	0	0.0000	0	0
	Total	105	0.0162	103	0.0159
UK	Direct	21	0.0006	23	0.0006
	Indirect	126	0.0035	158	0.0043
	Induced	0	0.0000	0	0
	Total	148	0.0041	181	0.0049
Spain	Direct	19	0.0009	20	0.0009
	Indirect	120	0.0054	138	0.0063
	Induced	0	0.0000	0	0
	Total	139	0.0063	159	0.0072

Table 6: Earnings as €millions and % of GDP.

3.3 GDP (Value added)

The value added reflects the additional income generated by producing goods and services, in other words it's the contribution of capital and labour to the production process. In Ireland, the X-Rotor technology creates more value added as a percentage of GDP than traditional HAWTs, most of which is from indirect effects. The opposite is seen for the UK and Spain where traditional HAWTs add more value to the economy than X-Rotor. This pattern was expected as HAWTs require a larger amount of capital to be invested creating more value in countries where they can be manufactured. The additional GDP for HAWTs compared with X-Rotor is 0.0017% for UK, and 0.0016% Spain (Table 7).

As is seen, the smaller economy in terms of the GDP captures larger effects when such a big project as 5 GW of offshore wind is deployed. Ireland shows a X-ROTOR effect on GDP of 0.0581%, followed by Spain 0.0154%

¹⁰ See <https://data.oecd.org/gdp/gross-domestic-product-gdp.htm> for US\$ GDP and <https://www.centralbank.ie/statistics/interest-rates-exchange-rates/exchange-rates> for mean exchange rates to Euro, accessed on 26-Feb-2024

and lastly UK 0.0099%. However, the small numbers should not be underestimated as the GDP of these three regions are quite large, see above.

Country	Effect	X-ROTOR	HAWTs
Ireland	Direct	0.0084	0.0057
	Indirect	0.0497	0.0318
	Induced	0	0
	Total	0.0581	0.0375
UK	Direct	0.0014	0.0015
	Indirect	0.0085	0.0101
	Induced	0.000	0
	Total	0.0099	0.0116
Spain	Direct	0.0022	0.0023
	Indirect	0.0133	0.0146
	Induced	0	0
	total	0.0154	0.0170

Table 7: Value added as a % of GDP.

3.4 Total Output

The last part of the results presents total output generated in each region by each technology (Table 8). It is important to recall that, approximately €20 billion is being fed into each economy irrespective of the technology. The first thing to note is that the output is on average more than double this input for each region. However, depending on the total percentage of spending and manufacturing in each country, Spain and UK have the largest output of €52 billion. As with the number of jobs the effect on total output from X-ROTOR in Ireland is slightly larger, 0.0409% of GDP, than the effect from HAWTs. It is the reverse for Spain and the UK, and by larger margins of 0.1448% and 0.1209% respectively. Looking at the normalised results, the output generated as a percentage of GDP is very high for Ireland due to the fact that it's a smaller country than Spain, leaving UK with the largest GDP with the smallest normalised effect.

Country	Effect	X-ROTOR		HAWTs	
		Total Output Generated € m	GDP (%)	Total Output Generated € m	GDP (%)
Ireland	Direct	9,709	1.4914	9,617	1.4773
	Indirect	13,310	2.0446	13,088	2.0104
	Induced	9,227	1.4173	8,959	1.3764
	Total	32,246	4.9533	31,664	4.8639
UK	Direct	15,721	0.4303	16,526	0.4523
	Indirect	19,943	0.5458	22,830	0.6248
	Induced	15,594	0.4268	16,319	0.4466
	Total	51,904	1.4028	61,822	1.5237
Spain	Direct	13,866	0.6277	14,597	0.6608
	Indirect	24,566	1.1121	20,007	0.9057
	Induced	13,472	0.6099	14,098	0.6382

Total	51,904	2.3497	47,702	2.2047
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Table 8: Total output generated by a 5GW deployment over 30 years in € million.

It is important to note the induced effect is captured in the total output results (Table 8). In each region and by all technologies, the total output from induced exceeds the total output from direct effect. This shows that the model successfully captured the amount of money from direct activities that are spent (several times) in other economic sectors.

4 Conclusion

This report compares the effect of X-ROTOR deployment and the deployment of traditional HAWTs in Ireland, UK, and Spain. The principal areas of interest are the effect on jobs and GDP. The difference in job requirements between X-ROTOR deployment and that of traditional HAWTs, is that X-ROTOR requires about 10% fewer jobs averaged over Ireland, UK, and Spain. This is because X-ROTOR is a less expensive technology with a lower LCOE. These results depend heavily on the exact costs of the two technologies (Table 4), the assumptions for local spending (Table 2), and on the average gross salaries in each country. As X-ROTOR is more efficient, it requires a smaller investment, which has a smaller direct and indirect impact on local economies. The assumptions in Table 2 are based on the smaller size of the turbines and shorter blades of X-ROTOR compared with HAWTs, and hence the greater ease of manufacture with less need to import the components. The figures for salaries, though based on reliable sources, are without the effect of wage convergence which may happen in the offshore wind industry as workers move across borders, but speculation about such convergence is beyond the scope of this report.

There are clear differences between the three countries. There are fewer jobs projected to be created in Ireland. This is because of the lack of a tradition of heavy industry, shipbuilding, and mechanical engineering. There are more local jobs in Spain which has such industries and yet more in the UK which already has an offshore wind industry. The effect of offshore wind of either technology on GDP is largest for Ireland, less for Spain, and least for the UK. This is due to the relative sizes of the three economies.

The objective of this report was to examine the direct effects of X-ROTOR deployment in three European countries, Ireland, UK, and Spain. This report has used a “bottom up” approach using the I-JEDI model from NREL to calculate estimates for the effect of X-ROTOR and HAWTs on employment, earnings, GDP and total output. This approach is complementary to that of our colleagues Williamson and Allan (2023) who used a CGE method in Deliverable 7.8. Compared to the results in our colleagues’ central scenario, where X-ROTOR alone is deployed in the UK, we find the I-JEDI model estimates slightly over 27,000 jobs compared with the CGE model which estimates 29,500 jobs. Regarding the effect on GDP, the I-JEDI model estimates an increase in GDP of 0.07% compared with an increase of 0.48% from the CGE model. This difference is the result of the CGE model taking into account the secondary effect of lower electricity prices for the whole UK economy in the event of a complete adoption of X-ROTOR instead of HAWTs. While this is unlikely to happen, the result

nonetheless shows the difference between the two modelling systems, namely that a bottom-up model, such as presented here, does not examine the whole economy but focuses on the immediate effects. The results for the numbers of jobs from X-ROTOR shows that both models are in agreement carrying out their basic calculations. While the authors are more than aware of the estimated nature of the results in this report, it seems clear that X-ROTOR's greater efficiency means that it can produce power for a lower cost than HAWTs, and that the costs during the lifetime of an X-ROTOR wind farm will be lower than HAWTs.

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